

Learner Autonomy Based on Constructivism Learning Theory

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Abstract : Constructivism learning theory lays emphasis on the learners' active learning, such as learning initiative, sociality and context. By analyzing the relationship between constructivism learning theory and learner autonomy, this paper explores how to cultivate learners' learner autonomy under the guidance of constructivism learning theory.

Keywords : constructivism learning theory, learner autonomy, relationship, cultivation

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